

D8.8

Yearly Communication Impact Report

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1. Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are a central part of the BBTWINS project to ensure that the project activities, results, and technology are communicated to the relevant stakeholders in a clear, consistent and effective manner.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.5) identified the main objectives for communicating and disseminating the BBTWINS project, the key stakeholders to be targeted, and the strategy for engaging with them to maximise opportunities for the project results to be exploited at a national and a European level.

This document is the final report tracking the communication key performance indicators and their targets. First, the tables of KPIs are displayed below, followed by the impact report. This period is for M37-M48.

2. Overview of the Project

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aimed to develop a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bioprocessing. The platform was based on 'digital twins' technology – creating a real-time digital replica of physical processes in the agri-food industry. BBTWINS also combined Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, the Internet of Things (IoT) and software analytics in this single platform.

With 13 partners in 7 countries, the BBTWINS consortium was focusing on meat and fruit production, integrating the value chain (from crop to final product) and defined the optimal pathway for each feedstock to maximise efficiency and minimise losses – without impacting quality.

2.1. Introduction

The BBTWINS Yearly Communication Impact Report helps track the communication and dissemination of key performance indicators (KPIs) as part of ensuring a comprehensive communication and dissemination of BBTWINS.

Communicating with stakeholders is a key challenge, both to inform them of project activities and results, but also to ensure the uptake of project technology and ensure the project's lasting impact. To facilitate this communication, the project will reach out to stakeholders throughout the project to raise awareness of the added value of digitalisation in agri-food value chains in achieving increased resource efficiency, as well as to highlight the potential of BBTWINS technology.

2.2. Objectives

The main aim of WP8 'Communication and Dissemination' is to advance and enhance the impact and results of the BBTWINS project around Europe and beyond. To achieve this, the Communication and Dissemination plan (D8.5) put in place a strategy to deliver project activities, engage stakeholders, and ensure the outcomes of the project are exploited. This overarching communication and dissemination plan also requires strategies for both internal and external communication.

The plan sets out a clear overview of how all communication channels, activities, and tools work together to engage with the relevant stakeholder groups. WP8 overlaps with all other work packages apart from WP9 Project Management.

3. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs of the BBTWINS project are there to provide direction to the communication and dissemination efforts. The KPIs listed below (Table 3) were monitored internally, with impact reports created annually (deliverables 8.2, 8.6, 8.7 and 8.8) showing progress on reaching these KPIs (M12, M24, M36 and M48). The detailed performance of the project against the specific KPIs below will be reported in the Review Report #3 for confidentiality reasons. The current document via its Annex shows the performance of the project in a deliverable of public nature.

Table 1 Updated List of KPIs as declared in D8.5

<u>Dissemination Products</u>	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Press releases	2	2	2	2
Quarterly Newsletter	4	4	4	4
(# of project subscribers)	500	150	300	500
(Opening rate per list segment)	25%	25%	30%	40%
Media Kit	1			
Press articles/media coverage	5	5	5	5
Specialised press – feature articles	1	2	2	2
(# of views / print dissemination)	100	500	500	500
Peer reviewed Open Access publications	2	1	1	1
Joint private-public publications	2	2	2	2
Videos				
Introductory project video	1			
Project videos	7	7	7	7
Use case highlight videos			1	1
(# of views in total)			800	1000
Data visualization and digital journey			2	2
(# of users)			250	400
<u>Dissemination / Clustering activities</u>				
Stakeholder consultations	2	2	2	2
Workshops				
(# of events organised per year)	1		1	1
(# of attendees per event organised)	50		50	100
(# of views per recorded webinar)	60		170	220
Mid-term Workshop & Results Conference			1	
(# of attendees)			150	
Final International Conference				1
(# of attendee)				200
Event participation				
(# of conferences, workshops, pitch events, trade fairs, other)	10	10	10	10
Activities Co-organised w/ CBE JU projects	1	1	1	1

4. Annex

4.1. Annual Impact Report

Media Relations

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total planned	Total achieved
Press Releases	2	4	1	1	8	8
Press articles/media coverage	20	10	7	2	20	39
Specialised press/feature articles	1	2	2	2	5	7

Scientific Publications

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total planned	Total achieved
Peer-reviewed open access publications	0	1	0	1	5	2
Joint private-public publications	0	2	0	2	8	4

Events

Events	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total planned	Total achieved
Events attended:	18	14	21	9	40	62
Workshops/conferences organised:	1	0	1	2	3	4
Activities co-organised with other JU projects	1	1	1	1	5	4
Stakeholder consultations	0	2	2	2	8	8

Newsletter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total planned	Total achieved
Total newsletters	2	3	4	3	16	12
Subscribers	102	164	169	442	500	442
Opening rate	26.5%	33.5%	43.1%	37%	40%	35% (avg)

Videos

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Total planned	Total achieved
Videos	2	9	9	8	34	36
Total views	276	995	2537	5315	2550	5315
Yearly update video	1	1	1	0	4	3
Use case highlight videos	0	0	1	3	2	4
Final conference videos				2	1	4

Website Overview

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Users	1,448	3,848	1,707	3,233
Views	5,088	6,230	5,461	6,055
Engagement Rate	30.41%	29.30%	45.95%	35%

Twitter

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4**
Total Followers	104	142	173	NA
Impressions	10,156	4,393	16,440	NA
Engagement Rate*	3.6%	3.8%	9.35%	NA

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

** **Footnote: Discontinuation of X (formerly Twitter)**

Due to declining engagement, safety concerns, misinformation, and added burden of not being able to access the analytics for content optimisation, we've shifted focus from X to LinkedIn to better reach professional audiences and maximise impact.

LinkedIn

Dissemination Products	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
Total Followers	302	531	628	898
Impressions	7,374	6,750	22,726	48,379
Engagement Rate*	4.99%	10.8%	4.4%	15.2%

*Engagement rates measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality. The scaling and methodology used for LinkedIn has been fine-tuned, providing a more accurate number.

